

Narrative Review on Materials Used in Pulpotomy: Past, Present, and Future

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Abstract

Pulpotomy is a well-established dental procedure designed to maintain the health of radicular pulp in cariously or traumatically exposed teeth. The choice of material used during pulpotomy plays a critical role in the long-term success of the procedure. Over the decades, pulpotomy materials have evolved significantly, from early use of formocresol to contemporary materials such as mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), biodentine, and calcium silicate-based bio-ceramics. This review provides a comprehensive analysis of the historical evolution, current trends, and future directions of materials used in pulpotomy, discussing their biological properties, clinical effectiveness, and long-term outcomes. We also explored novel bioactive materials and regenerative therapies currently being investigated.

Introduction

Finn (1991) defined pulpotomy as the complete removal of the coronal portion of the dental pulp, followed by placement of a suitable dressing or medicament that will promote healing and preserve vitality of the tooth.¹

According to AAPD (1998), pulpotomy is defined as the surgical amputation of affected, infected coronal portion of the dental pulp preserving the vitality and function of the remaining part of radicular pulp (Figure 1).²

Pulpotomy is one of the most common procedures performed in pediatric and adult dentistry to treat carious or traumatically exposed pulp in primary and immature permanent teeth. The technique involves the removal of the coronal portion of the pulp, leaving the radicular pulp intact, followed by the placement of a medicament or dressing that promotes healing and prevents bacterial invasion. The success of a pulpotomy depends largely on the material used, as it must encourage healing of the remaining pulp tissue, promote the formation of a hard tissue barrier, and prevent infection. A variety of materials have been explored in pulpotomy, from early formulations like formocresol to advanced materials like bio-ceramics.³ This review provides a detailed exploration of the historical context, current materials, and future innovations in

pulpotomy, aiming to provide a thorough understanding of the evolution and potential future directions of this critical treatment modality.

Rationale:⁴

- Radicular pulp is healthy and capable of healing after surgical amputation of the infected coronal pulp.
- Preserves vitality of radicular pulp.
- Maintains tooth in a physiologic condition.

Indications of Pulpotomy:^{4,5} (Figure 2)

- Carious / mechanical exposure in vital asymptomatic tooth when their retention is more important than extraction.
- In a mixed dentition stage where the primary teeth is preferred over a space maintainer.
- Tooth free of radicular pulpitis.
- Absence of abscess or fistula.
- Permanent posterior tooth for the relief from pulpagia.
- Vital tooth with healthy periodontium.
- Spontaneous or persistent pain may or may not be present.
- Lack of clinical evidence of pulpal degeneration, such as pain on percus-

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sion, history of swelling or sinus tracts.

- Restorable teeth following completion of procedure.
- Following pulpal amputation, haemorrhage is bright red and easy to control, haemostasis could be easily achievable within 5 minutes with a sterile moist cotton pellet.
- In young permanent tooth with vital exposed pulp and incompletely formed apices.

Radiographic Inclusion Criteria^{4,5} was the following: (Figure 3)

- Radiolucency approaching pulp.
- Minimum of 2/3rd of the root length should be remaining.
- No interradicular/periapical radiolucency.
- Absence of radiographic signs of internal and external resorption.

Contraindications:^{3,5} (Figure 4)

- Persistent toothache.
- Tenderness on percussion.
- A non-restorable tooth with large carious lesion.
- Highly viscous, sluggish haemorrhage from canal orifice, which is uncontrollable.
- Medical contraindications like heart disease, immune-compromised patient.
- Swelling or fistula.
- A tooth with a mechanical or carious perforation of pulpal floor of the pulp chamber.
- Pathologic root resorption involving more than 1/3rd of the root.
- Pathologic loss of bone support resulting in loss of the normal periodontal attachment.
- The presence of dentigerous or follicular cyst.
- Radiographically presence of internal root resorption.
- Tooth close to natural exfoliation.
- Radiographic signs of calcific globules in pulp chamber.

The ideal dressing material for the radicular pulp should : 6

- Be bactericidal.
- Be harmless to the pulp and surrounding structures.
- Promote healing of the radicular pulp.
- Not interfere with the physiological process of root resorption.

Historical Perspective: Early Materials in Pulpotomy

Historically, the materials used in pulpotomy reflected a primary goal of preserving radicular pulp vitality and preventing bacterial ingress. Early approaches emphasized disinfection and fixation of the pulp tissue to achieve these aims. This section focuses on formocresol and other early materials.

Formocresol

Introduced by Buckley in 1904, formocresol became the gold standard for pulpotomy procedures in primary teeth for much of the 20th century. Formocresol is a combination of formaldehyde and cresol, diluted with glycerine and water. Its primary mechanism of action involves the fixation of pulp tissue, preventing further microbial invasion.⁶

Mechanism of Action of Formocresol

In spite of histologic studies that showed formalin, cresol and paraformaldehyde to be connective tissue irritants, it was

recognized early that formocresol is an efficient bactericide. It was also found to have the ability to prevent tissue autolysis by the complex chemical binding of formaldehyde with peptide groups of side chain amino acids without changing the basic structure of protein molecule.⁷

Advantages:^{6,8}

- A. Formocresol is highly effective in sterilizing the pulp chamber and preventing bacterial proliferation.
- B. It has a long-standing history of clinical success, with high initial success rates in primary teeth.

Disadvantages:^{6,8}

- A. The primary drawback of formocresol is its toxicity. Formaldehyde is a known carcinogen, raising concerns about the safety of its use, particularly in pediatric patients.
- B. Formocresol has been shown to cause pulp tissue necrosis beyond the area of application, potentially leading to internal root resorption and affecting long-term tooth retention.
- C. Concerns about systemic absorption and mutagenicity have led to its gradual phase-out in many parts of the world.

Histological Changes/Effects of Formocresol on pulp: Figure 5 (a), 5 (b)

Massler and Mansukhani (1959) conducted a detailed histologic investigation of the effect of formocresol on the pulps of 43 human primary teeth and permanent teeth in multiple treatment intervals.⁹

Fixation of the tissue directly under the medicament was apparent. After a 7 - 14 days application, the pulp develops three distinct zones.

- A broad eosinophilic zone of fixation.
- A broad pale staining zone with poor cellular definition.
- A zone of inflammation diffusing apically into normal pulp tissue.

In general, many histologic studies have shown several distinct zones following 60 days recall visits.

- Superficial debris along with the dentinal chips at the amputation site.
- Eosinophil stained and compressed tissue.
- A palely stained zone with loss of cellular definition.
- An area of fibrotic and inflammatory activity.
- An area of normal appearing pulp tissue considered to be vital.

Despite its success, the negative effects of formocresol led researchers to explore fewer toxic alternatives that could achieve similar clinical outcomes while promoting a more biologically favorable response.

Glutaraldehyde

Gravenmade(1974) has proposed glutaraldehyde as a fixative for pulp in dentistry. 2% Glutaraldehyde was introduced by **Kopel (1979)** and its properties were described by **Ranly (1982)** and **Kennedy (1986)**. The main principle of using glutaraldehyde is preservation of tissue. The presence of reparative dentin in almost all of the treated teeth confirms that the fixative effect of glutaraldehyde is limited to the pulpotomy site. This has been attributed to the cross-linking properties of glutaraldehyde.¹⁰

Advantages:^{6,11,12}

- It is initially more active chemically.
- It rapidly forms cross linkages and its penetration is more limited.
- Glutaraldehyde is not as volatile as formocresol.
- There is less apical damage and less necrosis in the glutaraldehyde treated specimens.
- There is no evidence of ingrowth of granulation tissue into the apex in the glutaraldehyde-treated specimens.
- There is less dystrophic calcification in the glutaraldehyde specimens.
- Reaction to pulp is irreversible.
- Molecules of glutaraldehyde do not diffuse out of apical foramen.
- It fixes tissue instantly and excess solution is unnecessary.
- It is not known to be cytotoxic, mutagenic or carcinogenic.
- It has no systemic toxic effects.

Disadvantages:^{6,11,12}

- Short shelf life.
- It has to be freshly prepared.
- Buffered solution has to be refrigerated.

Glutaraldehyde has no bactericidal ability at low pH and therefore must be alkalized to a pH of between 7.5 and 8.5 before it is effective. This increase in pH renders glutaraldehyde unstable, thus decreasing its shelf life to approximately 14 days.

Mechanism of Action

The pulp response to glutaraldehyde may lie somewhere between the 2 response mechanisms. The fixative, nonbiologic properties of glutaraldehyde do not promote cell proliferation. However, its deleterious effects are limited to tissue fixation without causing coagulation necrosis, that ultimately mineralizes and forms part of the bridge, as in the calcium hydroxide pulpotomy procedure. The lack of necrosis may be the expression of a tissue response to a mild, self-limited irritant, without the formation of dentin bridge.¹³

Histologic Features of Glutaraldehyde:¹²

- Less damage apically and less necrosis.
- Less clearly demarcated zones within radicular zones.
- No evidence of growth in granulation tissue.
- Less intense dystrophic calcification limited to coronal portion of the canal.
- Fibroblastic proliferation observed immediately below glutaraldehyde fixed tissue in coronal 3rd indicating repair replacement.

Ferric Sulfate

Ferric sulfate (Monsels Solution) emerged as an alternative to formocresol in the 1980s. It is a hemostatic agent that works by forming a protein coagulum that seals the pulp stump, preventing bacterial infiltration and allowing healing of the remaining pulp tissue.¹⁴

Advantages:^{15,16}

- Ferric sulfate is non-toxic compared to formocresol and provides effective hemostasis.
- It does not induce the same level of tissue necrosis as formocresol, preserving more of the radicular pulp tissue.

Disadvantages:^{15,16}

- Clinical studies have reported that while ferric sulfate has an initial high success rate, it may lead to internal resorption over time, possibly due to incomplete sealing or continued inflammation.
- It lacks the regenerative or hard tissue-inductive properties seen with more contemporary materials.

Mechanism of Action

On contact with blood, ferric sulfate forms a ferric ion-protein complex whose membrane mechanically seals the cut vessels, producing hemostasis. By forming plugs that occlude the capillary orifices, the protein complex also prevents the formation of blood clots and thereby minimizes chances for inflammation and internal resorption. Success rates of fs pulpotomies in primary molars have been reported to range from 81% to 97%.¹⁵

While ferric sulfate remains in use today, particularly in primary teeth, its lack of bioactivity and potential for resorption limit its utility in situations where long-term tooth preservation is essential.

The Advent of Biocompatible and Bioactive Materials As concerns over the cytotoxicity and limitations of early materials grew, the search for more biocompatible and bioactive materials led to the introduction of mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) and calcium hydroxide. These materials not only aim to preserve pulp vitality but also promote healing and regeneration of dentin.

Calcium Hydroxide

Hermann (1930) introduced calcium hydroxide as a pulp capping material. Calcium hydroxide has been widely used in various forms of vital pulp therapy, including pulpotomy, due to its ability to promote hard tissue formation and its antibacterial properties. This was pioneered by Teuscher & Zander (1938).^{8, 17}

Mechanism of Action

Calcium hydroxide stimulates pulp cells to form a dentinal bridge over the exposed pulp. The high pH (around 12) provides an antibacterial environment, further reducing the risk of infection.¹⁸

Advantages:¹⁸

- It is a cost-effective and easily available material.
- Its ability to induce the formation of a dentinal bridge has been well-documented in both primary and permanent teeth.

Disadvantages:¹⁸

- Dentinal bridges formed with calcium hydroxide are often incomplete or porous, which can allow bacterial ingress and lead to long-term failure.
- It has poor sealing properties, increasing the risk of leakage and subsequent pulp inflammation.
- Its mechanical properties are suboptimal, as it can disintegrate over time.

Histological Changes

- Bandi et al. (2017) found calcium hydroxide formed hard tissue barriers with mild inflammation and vital pulpal tissue underneath.¹⁹
- Nosrat et al. (2013) observed that calcium hydroxide paste caused greater inflammation and mummification,

likely due to its high alkalinity, with increasing inflammation over time and severe reactions from deep pulp maceration and debris inclusion.²⁰

Despite its historical significance, calcium hydroxide has largely been replaced by superior materials such as MTA, which offer better biological and clinical outcomes.

Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (MTA)

Mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), introduced in the early 1990s, revolutionized vital pulp therapy due to its superior properties compared to calcium hydroxide. Torabinejad et al. described some of the physical and chemical properties of MTA for pulpotomy procedures both in primary and young permanent teeth. MTA is composed primarily of tricalcium silicate, dicalcium silicate, and bismuth oxide (as a radiopacifier).^{21,22}

Mechanism of Action:²¹

MTA forms a hydroxyapatite-like structure upon setting, providing an excellent seal against bacterial leakage. It is highly biocompatible and induces the formation of a dentinal bridge by promoting the differentiation of odontoblast-like cells.

Advantages:²¹

- Excellent sealing properties, reducing the risk of bacterial microleakage.
- MTA is highly biocompatible and stimulates the formation of high-quality dentin at the pulp interface.
- Its success in clinical applications, particularly in pulpotomy, is well-documented, with high long-term success rates in both primary and permanent teeth.

Disadvantages:²¹

- MTA has a long setting time, often requiring the use of a moist cotton pellet and a secondary visit to complete the procedure.
- Its high cost and the difficulty in handling have been cited as limitations.
- The presence of bismuth oxide can cause discoloration, which is particularly concerning in anterior teeth.

Two Outcomes were Observed after MTA Pulpotomy.²³

- Few cases demonstrated the initial internal resorption, which stabilized after few months.
- Pulp Canal Obliteration (PCO) was observed due to progressive deposition of tertiary dentin and consequent narrowing of canals, which is a result of extensive activity of odontoblast-like cells indicating the presence of pulp vitality. Hence, it is considered not a failure.

Despite these drawbacks, MTA remains one of the most widely used and studied materials for pulpotomy due to its favorable biological and clinical properties. Numerous studies report higher success rates with MTA compared to traditional materials like formocresol and calcium hydroxide.

Contemporary Bioceramic Materials

In recent years, bioceramic materials have emerged as promising alternatives to traditional pulpotomy materials. These materials, designed to interact with the biological environment, offer superior biocompatibility and promote regenerative processes within the dental pulp.

Biodentine

Biodentine, introduced in the early 2010s, is a tricalcium

silicate-based material developed as an alternative to MTA. It has a faster setting time and better handling characteristics, making it ideal for use in single-visit procedures.²⁴

Mechanism of Action:²⁴

Like MTA, Biodentine promotes the release of calcium ions, which stimulate the formation of hydroxyapatite and encourage the differentiation of odontoblast-like cells. It sets quickly (within 12 minutes), forming a stable and durable barrier.

Advantages:²⁴

- Faster setting time compared to MTA, facilitating single-visit treatments.
- High biocompatibility and bioactivity, promoting dentin formation and sealing the pulp chamber effectively.
- Biodentine does not cause tooth discoloration, making it suitable for esthetic cases.

Disadvantages:²⁴

- Limited long-term clinical studies compared to MTA, although initial results are promising.
- Higher cost compared to traditional materials like calcium hydroxide and formocresol.

Calcium Silicate-based Bio-ceramics

Recent advancements in material science have led to the development of calcium silicate-based bio-ceramics, such as Endo-Sequence BC RRM (root repair material) and iRoot BP Plus, which offer excellent biological and clinical properties for pulpotomy procedures.²⁵

Mechanism of Action:²⁵

These materials release bioactive ions (primarily calcium ions) upon hydration, which interact with surrounding tissues to promote healing and regeneration. They form a chemical bond with dentin and provide an excellent seal against bacterial infiltration.

Advantages:²⁵

- Bioceramic materials offer superior biocompatibility, allowing for minimal inflammation and faster healing of pulp tissue.
- They have excellent sealing properties and bond chemically with the dentin, reducing the risk of bacterial leakage.
- Bio-ceramics are easy to handle and can be applied directly to the pulp, making them ideal for both primary and permanent teeth.

Disadvantages:²⁵

- These materials are relatively expensive compared to traditional options.
- Limited long-term clinical data is available, although initial studies indicate positive outcomes.

Future Directions: Regenerative Approaches and Biomaterials

The future of pulpotomy materials lies in regenerative endodontics and bioactive materials that go beyond simple pulp preservation. Regenerative therapies aim to harness the body's natural healing abilities to regenerate damaged pulp tissue and restore full function to the tooth.

Tissue Engineering and Stem Cell Therapy

Researchers are exploring the use of stem cells, growth factors, and scaffolds to regenerate dental pulp tissue. The

goal is to create materials that not only protect the remaining pulp but actively promote the growth of new pulp and dentin.²⁶

Stem cells from dental pulp (dental pulp stem cells, DPSCs) are capable of differentiating into odontoblast-like cells and forming new dentin. When combined with scaffolds made of collagen or other bioactive substances, these cells could potentially regenerate entire pulp-dentin complexes.²⁶ Growth factors such as transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) and bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) are being investigated for their ability to stimulate stem cell proliferation and differentiation within the pulp.²⁷

Bone Morphogenic Proteins

In 2003, Goldberg reported that there must be some stimulating agent which originated from bone and possibly a substance which is soluble in lymph tissue. Inducing substance when acting upon a responding cell i.e. - undifferentiated mesenchymal cells to become progenitor cell. Due to their amino acid sequences BMP-2 through BMP-9 are classified as belonging to transforming growth factor (TGF- β) superfamily.^{26,27}

For the Ideal Delivery, The Carrier Should be:²⁸

- Non - collagenous
- Immunogenetically inert
- Osteoconductive
- Bioabsorbable

Factors Influencing the Inductive Process of BMP:²⁸

- Timing of the response (considering both the exposure time required as well as the time of inducer is capable of inducing).
- Location or proximity of competent cells able to respond.
- Concentration.

Lyophilized Freeze-dried Platelet Derived Preparation

Platelet derived growth factor, insulin growth factor derived from platelet have generated considerable interest in the past. These compounds act as a signalling protein that could be directly involved in regulation of cell proliferation, migration and extra cellular matrix production in the dental pulp.²⁹

Enamel Matrix Proteins

Floratos and Kim (2017) conducted a study on enamel matrix derivative induced reparative dentin formation in a pulpotomy model in pig incisors. The findings demonstrated that enamel matrix molecules have the capacity to induce rapid wound pulpal healing in pulpotomized teeth, and suggest that longevity and continued presence of enamel matrix macromolecules at the application site can be utilized to stimulate growth and repair of dentin over a period consistent with a favourable outcome.³⁰

Sabbarani et al. (2008) stated that EMPs help in bio-induction of dentin formation. They reported clinical success rate of 90% and radiographic success rate of 60%.³¹

3D Printing of Biomaterials

Advances in 3D printing technology may allow for the creation of patient-specific scaffolds that can deliver stem cells and growth factors directly to the site of pulp damage. This technology has the potential to revolutionize the field of vital pulp therapy by creating custom-tailored regenerative

treatments for each patient.³²

Hydrogels and Injectable Biomaterials

Hydrogels and other injectable biomaterials are being developed to provide a minimally invasive means of delivering bioactive substances to the pulp chamber. These materials can be injected directly into the pulp cavity, where they form a gel-like structure that supports tissue regeneration.³²

Comparative Effectiveness of Pulpotomy Materials

A number of clinical studies have compared the effectiveness of various pulpotomy materials in terms of success rates, pulp vitality, and dentinal bridge formation.

Formocresol vs. MTA: Numerous studies have shown that MTA has a significantly higher long-term success rate than formocresol, particularly in terms of preserving pulp vitality and preventing resorption.

Calcium Hydroxide vs. MTA: While both materials promote dentinal bridge formation, MTA produces a complete and more durable barrier.

MTA vs. Biodentine: Biodentine shows comparable success rates to MTA but offers faster setting times and better handling properties, making it preferable for single-visit procedures.

Kalaskar and Damle et al. (2004) compared the efficiency of lyophilized freeze-dried platelet derived with calcium hydroxide as pulpotomy agents in primary molars. It was found that the success rate of lyophilized freeze-dried platelet derived pulpotomy proved to be more efficient.²⁸

Reasons for failure of Pulpotomy Therapy³³

Erroneous diagnosis of a chronically inflamed radicular pulp as non-inflamed and non-infected.

The irritating effect of eugenol as a component of the pulp space filling material.

Attempt to preserve a tooth with deep proximal carious lesions a condition leading to leakage due to incomplete coverage.

Signs of a failure can be seen on radiographic pathologic signs in pulp canal obliteration, sometimes termed as 'calcific metamorphosis' which can be seen in root canal of pulpotomized primary molars. In present scene, it is not considered a failure.

Conclusions

The materials used in pulpotomy have evolved dramatically from the early days of formocresol and calcium hydroxide to contemporary bio-ceramics and bioactive compounds. Mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) and Biodentine have set new standards for biocompatibility and clinical success, while calcium silicate-based bio-ceramics represent the next generation of materials for pulpotomy. Looking to the future, regenerative approaches using stem cells, growth factors, and advanced biomaterials hold the potential to transform pulpotomy from a treatment aimed at preserving pulp tissue to one that can regenerate damaged tissue and restore full function to the tooth.

As research into bioactive materials and regenerative techniques progresses, clinicians may soon have access to materials that not only seal and protect the pulp but actively contribute to its regeneration. In the meantime, materials like

MTA, Biodentine, and calcium silicate-based bio-ceramics remain the gold standard for achieving successful clinical outcomes in pulpotomy.

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Figure 1: Pulpotomy

Figure 2: Clinical Inclusion Criteria

Figure 3: Radiographic Evidence for Pulpotomy

Figure 4: Radiographic Evidence

Figure 5(A): Histological zones of formocresol pulpotomy

Figure 5(B): Histological zones of formocresol pulpotomy